

Table 3: HD95 [mm] of all 16 structures versus individual contours (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	15.7 (3.4 – 34.9)	6.0 (2.1 – 31.4)	6.0 (1.1 – 23.8)	5.9 (2.2 – 28.4)
Atrium_R	29.9 (7.6 – 93.2)	7.4 (2.5 – 17.8)	7.6 (2.1 – 18.0)	6.0 (2.4 – 19.6)
Ventricle_R	30.0 (10.4 – 77.7)	6.9 (3.0 – 24.0)	7.4 (2.0 – 26.1)	5.8 (2.7 – 30.0)
Ventricle_L	11.6 (6.0 – 122.2)	5.8 (2.9 – 26.4)	6.2 (2.1 – 32.8)	4.8 (2.0 – 20.4)
A_Aorta	33.6 (5.3 – 248.0)	6.7 (2.1 – 92.3)	6.2 (1.1 – 90.1)	6.0 (2.0 – 125.6)
A_Pulmonary	11.0 (4.0 – 52.5)	8.4 (3.0 – 51.5)	7.8 (1.5 – 52.0)	8.9 (2.1 – 50.3)
A_LAD		29.4 (2.0 – 97.5)		15.4 (2.0 – 93.5)
A_LCX		21.1 (2.0 – 84.7)		27.6 (2.1 – 85.1)
A_LM		4.4 (2.0 – 106.5)		14.1 (1.1 – 90.6)
A_RCA		27.7 (3.6 – 102.7)		18.5 (1.1 – 68.8)
V_Venacava_I	11.0 (2.2 – 103.0)	19.4 (3.2 – 89.7)	10.0 (2.0 – 112.3)	14.0 (4.0 – 78.7)
V_Venacava_S	26.5 (10.6 – 111.2)	10.0 (3.0 – 108.0)	11.4 (1.5 – 110.4)	14.0 (2.1 – 99.1)
Valve_Aortic		14.1 (2.0 – 87.9)		16.8 (4.9 – 82.8)
Valve_Pulmonic		10.5 (2.3 – 90.1)		12.8 (2.1 – 98.6)
Valve_Mitral		9.1 (2.0 – 37.5)		9.7 (3.8 – 38.4)
Valve_Tricuspid		12.7 (5.3 – 82.3)		12.0 (4.3 – 69.4)

Table 3: HD95 [mm] of all 16 structures versus individual contours (CECT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	25.5 (5.5 – 52.0)	5.6 (2.0 – 28.7)	5.1 (1.9 – 27.1)	4.6 (2.2 – 28.4)
Atrium_R	26.4 (9.8 – Inf)	7.3 (4.0 – 14.6)	6.9 (2.4 – 15.5)	6.0 (2.4 – 22.2)
Ventricle_R	38.0 (24.6 – Inf)	6.1 (3.3 – 24.0)	6.4 (2.7 – 24.0)	5.4 (2.7 – 26.0)
Ventricle_L	19.6 (12.0 – Inf)	5.4 (2.4 – 26.8)	5.4 (2.0 – 26.6)	4.5 (2.0 – 20.4)
A_Aorta	44.3 (6.2 – 264.9)	6.1 (2.2 – 95.4)	8.0 (1.3 – 85.6)	6.0 (1.3 – 101.9)
A_Pulmonary	20.1 (4.4 – 60.2)	7.6 (3.8 – 52.2)	7.3 (2.1 – 51.7)	8.3 (2.1 – 51.7)
A_LAD		55.3 (1.8 – 94.9)		25.3 (0.9 – 93.5)
A_LCX		14.9 (1.9 – 85.0)		35.3 (1.5 – 85.1)
A_LM		5.3 (1.5 – 107.6)		16.3 (0.9 – 90.6)
A_RCA		34.5 (2.7 – 107.8)		26.8 (1.1 – 68.8)
V_Venacava_I	Inf (6.2 – Inf)	16.2 (3.5 – 110.8)	10.6 (4.0 – 110.9)	12.0 (4.0 – 78.7)
V_Venacava_S	30.1	10.6 (2.7 – 108.0)	12.1 (2.1 – 108.0)	12.2 (2.1 – 99.1)
Valve_Aortic		16.3 (6.0 – 59.0)		18.3 (4.0 – 48.3)
Valve_Pulmonic		10.0 (2.9 – 87.2)		13.8 (2.1 – 98.6)
Valve_Mitral		9.9 (2.4 – 38.4)		10.4 (2.7 – 38.4)
Valve_Tricuspid		11.6 (2.7 – 80.0)		12.1 (4.5 – 69.4)

Table 4: HD95 [mm] of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	10.5 (6.9 – 29.7)	4.7 (3.6 – 8.8)	5.2 (3.9 – 9.4)	
Atrium_R	36.3 (11.0 – 88.4)	6.2 (4.5 – 7.4)	6.4 (4.9 – 9.4)	
Ventricle_R	56.7 (14.0 – 71.6)	6.0 (5.4 – 8.6)	6.6 (5.2 – 7.9)	
Ventricle_L	16.0 (6.2 – 98.6)	4.0 (2.7 – 10.8)	4.0 (3.6 – 18.1)	
A_Aorta	43.4 (18.3 – 147.9)	3.6 (2.0 – 11.8)	4.2 (2.9 – 15.7)	
A_Pulmonary	9.0 (2.5 – 35.2)	10.3 (2.9 – 24.2)	9.4 (6.0 – 24.0)	
A_LAD		47.8 (3.0 – 87.3)		
A_LCX		45.0 (10.5 – 77.6)		
A_LM		11.3 (2.1 – 24.5)		
A_RCA		47.5 (12.4 – 58.3)		
V_Venacava_I	20.4 (8.6 – 38.9)	21.0 (6.0 – 32.1)	15.6 (6.3 – 30.0)	
V_Venacava_S	34.7 (24.4 – 82.0)	14.0 (8.1 – 29.3)	17.2 (9.0 – 27.0)	
Valve_Aortic		14.4 (6.6 – 20.3)		
Valve_Pulmonic		12.4 (10.7 – 82.5)		
Valve_Mitral		7.0 (5.0 – 12.9)		
Valve_Tricuspid		13.5 (9.4 – 21.1)		

Table 4: HD95 [mm] of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (CECT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	18.4 (7.9 – 43.8)	4.2 (2.7 – 8.5)	4.5 (2.9 – 8.5)	
Atrium_R	20.8 (13.2 – Inf)	7.0 (5.1 – 9.7)	7.4 (5.4 – 7.9)	
Ventricle_R	36.8 (32.1 – Inf)	4.9 (4.1 – 9.1)	5.8 (4.3 – 9.9)	
Ventricle_L	23.4 (20.0 – Inf)	5.2 (3.6 – 7.4)	5.8 (2.4 – 8.0)	
A_Aorta	47.5 (12.0 – 162.8)	5.0 (3.1 – 8.9)	6.1 (3.0 – 11.0)	
A_Pulmonary	13.5 (4.0 – 55.7)	10.0 (6.9 – 27.1)	8.9 (8.0 – 25.7)	
A_LAD		77.6 (11.1 – 92.1)		
A_LCX		56.8 (11.3 – 78.4)		
A_LM		21.1 (6.8 – 29.3)		
A_RCA		55.7 (22.2 – 66.2)		
V_Venacava_I	Inf (39.4 – Inf)	18.7 (6.6 – 48.4)	15.1 (6.0 – 34.0)	
V_Venacava_S	30.6 (20.2 – 62.6)	12.2 (7.5 – 18.0)	16.6 (7.2 – 31.7)	
Valve_Aortic		16.2 (10.5 – 27.2)		
Valve_Pulmonic		12.6 (7.9 – 79.8)		
Valve_Mitral		7.1 (3.8 – 8.1)		
Valve_Tricuspid		9.5 (8.6 – 12.0)		

Table 5: VR of all 16 structures versus individual contours (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	1.4 (1.0 – 2.9)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.5)	1.2 (1.0 – 1.9)
Atrium_R	3.3 (1.0 – 593.3)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.2)
Ventricle_R	2.0 (1.0 – 170.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.7)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.5)
Ventricle_L	1.2 (1.0 – 19.7)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.5)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.1)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.9)
A_Aorta	1.5 (1.0 – 3.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 3.1)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.9)	1.2 (1.0 – 3.5)
A_Pulmonary	1.2 (1.0 – 2.4)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.1)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.0)	1.3 (1.0 – 2.4)
A_LAD		1.8 (1.0 – 10.6)		2.9 (1.0 – 23.6)
A_LCX		2.8 (1.0 – 57.8)		3.9 (1.1 – 91.0)
A_LM		1.5 (1.0 – 5.9)		3.4 (1.0 – 21.3)
A_RCA		2.1 (1.0 – 150.8)		3.2 (1.0 – 239.8)
V_Venacava_I	2.5 (1.0 – Inf)	1.6 (1.0 – 6.3)	1.4 (1.0 – 3.5)	1.8 (1.0 – 5.1)
V_Venacava_S	4.5 (1.1 – 50.5)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.9)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.8)	1.5 (1.0 – 4.7)
Valve_Aortic		2.4 (1.0 – 36.6)		4.6 (1.0 – 61.6)
Valve_Pulmonic		1.7 (1.0 – 32.6)		3.5 (1.0 – 68.7)
Valve_Mitral		1.5 (1.0 – 21.6)		2.8 (1.1 – 68.3)
Valve_Tricuspid		1.6 (1.0 – 27.7)		3.3 (1.0 – 93.8)

Table 5: VR of all 16 structures versus individual contours

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	2.5 (1.0 – 3.3)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.5)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.9)
Atrium_R	7.5 (1.1 – Inf)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.7)	1.2 (1.0 – 2.2)
Ventricle_R	12.1 (1.5 – Inf)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.4)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.4)	1.2 (1.0 – 1.6)
Ventricle_L	1.7 (1.0 – Inf)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.6)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.8)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.9)
A_Aorta	2.4 (1.1 – 53.5)	1.1 (1.0 – 3.1)	1.1 (1.0 – 3.1)	1.2 (1.0 – 3.5)
A_Pulmonary	1.4 (1.1 – 8.0)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.2)	1.1 (1.0 – 2.3)	1.3 (1.0 – 2.6)
A_LAD		1.9 (1.0 – 7.3)		3.3 (1.0 – 23.6)
A_LCX		1.7 (1.0 – 14.8)		4.9 (1.0 – 91.0)
A_LM		1.4 (1.0 – 7.8)		4.0 (1.0 – 21.3)
A_RCA		2.4 (1.1 – 13.4)		3.3 (1.0 – 239.8)
V_Venacava_I	Inf (1.3 – Inf)	1.5 (1.0 – 5.4)	1.4 (1.0 – 4.6)	1.8 (1.0 – 8.0)
V_Venacava_S	8.4 (1.1 – Inf)	1.3 (1.0 – 3.7)	1.2 (1.0 – 3.7)	1.5 (1.0 – 5.1)
Valve_Aortic		2.1 (1.1 – 12.1)		5.8 (1.0 – 61.6)
Valve_Pulmonic		1.8 (1.0 – 20.2)		3.9 (1.1 – 68.7)
Valve_Mitral		1.6 (1.0 – 35.2)		3.0 (1.0 – 68.3)
Valve_Tricuspid		1.6 (1.0 – 37.9)		3.7 (1.1 – 93.8)

(CECT)

Table 6: VR of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	1.3 (1.2 – 2.8)	1.2 (1.2 – 1.3)	1.2 (1.2 – 1.3)	
Atrium_R	5.9 (1.4 – 567.3)	1.2 (1.1 – 1.3)	1.2 (1.1 – 1.4)	
Ventricle_R	23.9 (1.4 – 171.2)	1.3 (1.1 – 1.3)	1.3 (1.1 – 1.4)	
Ventricle_L	1.7 (1.1 – 17.4)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.1)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.4)	
A_Aorta	2.2 (1.4 – 3.4)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.3)	1.2 (1.0 – 1.3)	
A_Pulmonary	1.3 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.3 (1.2 – 1.5)	1.3 (1.2 – 1.6)	
A_LAD		6.0 (1.4 – 9.9)		
A_LCX		5.7 (1.5 – 69.8)		
A_LM		3.5 (1.4 – 8.4)		
A_RCA		6.3 (3.0 – 50.1)		
V_Venacava_I	4.3 (1.8 – Inf)	2.4 (1.2 – 3.7)	2.2 (1.4 – 2.8)	
V_Venacava_S	6.3 (2.8 – 49.6)	1.6 (1.4 – 2.4)	1.7 (1.4 – 2.4)	
Valve_Aortic		2.6 (1.7 – 4.2)		
Valve_Pulmonic		3.0 (2.1 – 8.7)		
Valve_Mitral		2.2 (1.6 – 5.0)		
Valve_Tricuspid		3.7 (1.9 – 6.1)		

Table 6: VR of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (CECT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	2.2 (1.1 – 3.2)	1.2 (1.1 – 1.2)	1.2 (1.1 – 1.2)	
Atrium_R	6.6 (1.9 – Inf)	1.2 (1.0 – 1.4)	1.2 (1.0 – 1.3)	
Ventricle_R	9.0 (2.2 – Inf)	1.2 (1.2 – 1.3)	1.2 (1.2 – 1.3)	
Ventricle_L	1.8 (1.5 – Inf)	1.1 (1.1 – 1.2)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.2)	
A_Aorta	2.4 (1.3 – 49.3)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.2)	1.1 (1.0 – 1.3)	
A_Pulmonary	1.4 (1.0 – 8.0)	1.3 (1.2 – 1.4)	1.3 (1.1 – 1.4)	
A_LAD		6.0 (1.2 – 9.2)		
A_LCX		6.6 (2.0 – 8.4)		
A_LM		4.7 (1.4 – 11.2)		
A_RCA		6.0 (1.7 – 21.5)		
V_Venacava_I	Inf (2.6 – Inf)	2.4 (1.1 – 3.2)	2.2 (1.3 – 3.3)	
V_Venacava_S	9.8 (4.5 – Inf)	1.7 (1.0 – 2.1)	1.8 (1.4 – 2.0)	
Valve_Aortic		3.7 (2.2 – 5.1)		
Valve_Pulmonic		3.5 (3.1 – 8.5)		
Valve_Mitral		2.1 (1.4 – 2.3)		
Valve_Tricuspid		2.7 (1.9 – 3.0)		

Table 1: DSC of all 16 structures versus individual contours (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	0.78 (0.28 – 0.93)	0.89 (0.60 – 0.96)	0.90 (0.61 – 0.98)	0.90 (0.67 – 0.97)
Atrium_R	0.44 (0.00 – 0.89)	0.88 (0.63 – 0.94)	0.87 (0.65 – 0.97)	0.90 (0.61 – 0.97)
Ventricle_R	0.58 (0.01 – 0.85)	0.88 (0.64 – 0.95)	0.87 (0.63 – 0.98)	0.89 (0.57 – 0.96)
Ventricle_L	0.86 (0.02 – 0.92)	0.91 (0.57 – 0.96)	0.91 (0.58 – 0.98)	0.93 (0.52 – 0.97)
A_Aorta	0.70 (0.30 – 0.91)	0.89 (0.46 – 0.95)	0.90 (0.47 – 0.96)	0.90 (0.44 – 0.96)
A_Pulmonary	0.78 (0.31 – 0.91)	0.84 (0.32 – 0.93)	0.85 (0.35 – 0.96)	0.83 (0.39 – 0.94)
A_LAD		0.35 (0.00 – 0.81)		0.46 (0.08 – 0.87)
A_LCX		0.21 (0.00 – 0.80)		0.35 (0.02 – 0.86)
A_LM		0.48 (0.11 – 0.84)		0.43 (0.09 – 0.94)
A_RCA		0.32 (0.00 – 0.69)		0.40 (0.01 – 0.90)
V_Venacava_I	0.53 (0.00 – 0.90)	0.59 (0.24 – 0.87)	0.69 (0.39 – 0.92)	0.67 (0.33 – 0.91)
V_Venacava_S	0.31 (0.04 – 0.74)	0.79 (0.47 – 0.92)	0.78 (0.47 – 0.93)	0.77 (0.35 – 0.95)
Valve_Aortic		0.37 (0.00 – 0.92)		0.32 (0.03 – 0.91)
Valve_Pulmonic		0.37 (0.00 – 0.90)		0.43 (0.03 – 0.88)
Valve_Mitral		0.39 (0.00 – 0.86)		0.49 (0.03 – 0.82)
Valve_Tricuspid		0.26 (0.00 – 0.63)		0.39 (0.00 – 0.80)

Table 1: DSC of all 16 structures versus individual contours (CECT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus Median (min – max)
Atrium_L	0.56 (0.27 – 0.91)	0.91 (0.61 – 0.96)	0.91 (0.61 – 0.97)	0.92 (0.67 – 0.97)
Atrium_R	0.23 (0.00 – 0.74)	0.89 (0.68 – 0.93)	0.89 (0.71 – 0.97)	0.90 (0.63 – 0.95)
Ventricle_R	0.11 (0.00 – 0.63)	0.88 (0.70 – 0.95)	0.88 (0.70 – 0.93)	0.89 (0.76 – 0.95)
Ventricle_L	0.70 (0.00 – 0.82)	0.92 (0.55 – 0.96)	0.92 (0.52 – 0.97)	0.93 (0.52 – 0.97)
A_Aorta	0.58 (0.04 – 0.89)	0.88 (0.47 – 0.94)	0.88 (0.47 – 0.97)	0.90 (0.44 – 0.96)
A_Pulmonary	0.75 (0.13 – 0.90)	0.85 (0.31 – 0.92)	0.85 (0.34 – 0.93)	0.84 (0.39 – 0.94)
A_LAD		0.30 (0.00 – 0.81)		0.45 (0.08 – 0.89)
A_LCX		0.35 (0.04 – 0.67)		0.30 (0.02 – 0.84)
A_LM		0.43 (0.02 – 0.79)		0.39 (0.09 – 0.89)
A_RCA		0.32 (0.04 – 0.68)		0.41 (0.01 – 0.88)
V_Venacava_I	0.00 (0.00 – 0.72)	0.57 (0.15 – 0.77)	0.64 (0.24 – 0.84)	0.67 (0.22 – 0.91)
V_Venacava_S	0.19 (0.00 – 0.57)	0.74 (0.08 – 0.87)	0.74 (0.12 – 0.87)	0.78 (0.22 – 0.94)
Valve_Aortic		0.30 (0.00 – 0.77)		0.29 (0.03 – 0.88)
Valve_Pulmonic		0.34 (0.00 – 0.85)		0.38 (0.03 – 0.88)
Valve_Mitral		0.46 (0.02 – 0.80)		0.46 (0.03 – 0.85)
Valve_Tricuspid		0.27 (0.00 – 0.78)		0.38 (0.00 – 0.80)

Table 2: DSC of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (planning CT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	0.86 (0.52 – 0.88)	0.91 (0.87 – 0.91)	0.90 (0.87 – 0.92)	
Atrium_R	0.32 (0.00 – 0.83)	0.89 (0.85 – 0.92)	0.89 (0.81 – 0.92)	
Ventricle_R	0.14 (0.01 – 0.81)	0.87 (0.83 – 0.92)	0.87 (0.83 – 0.91)	
Ventricle_L	0.75 (0.02 – 0.91)	0.94 (0.83 – 0.96)	0.94 (0.81 – 0.95)	
A_Aorta	0.61 (0.45 – 0.84)	0.89 (0.84 – 0.96)	0.90 (0.88 – 0.95)	
A_Pulmonary	0.84 (0.72 – 0.93)	0.84 (0.75 – 0.90)	0.83 (0.77 – 0.89)	
A_LAD		0.30 (0.17 – 0.75)		
A_LCX		0.21 (0.03 – 0.72)		
A_LM		0.42 (0.20 – 0.75)		
A_RCA		0.29 (0.00 – 0.44)		
V_Venacava_I	0.38 (0.00 – 0.70)	0.57 (0.38 – 0.79)	0.61 (0.53 – 0.74)	
V_Venacava_S	0.27 (0.04 – 0.52)	0.74 (0.59 – 0.84)	0.72 (0.58 – 0.84)	
Valve_Aortic		0.53 (0.36 – 0.71)		
Valve_Pulmonic		0.47 (0.20 – 0.63)		
Valve_Mitral		0.60 (0.25 – 0.69)		
Valve_Tricuspid		0.37 (0.25 – 0.52)		

Table 2: DSC of all 16 structures versus consensus contour (CECT)

Structure	Model A Median (min – max)	Model B/B* Median (min – max)	Model C Median (min – max)	Manual consensus (not applicable)
Atrium_L	0.66 (0.48 – 0.89)	0.92 (0.88 – 0.95)	0.92 (0.88 – 0.95)	
Atrium_R	0.30 (0.00 – 0.69)	0.89 (0.82 – 0.92)	0.89 (0.86 – 0.93)	
Ventricle_R	0.28 (0.00 – 0.60)	0.88 (0.83 – 0.92)	0.89 (0.84 – 0.91)	
Ventricle_L	0.68 (0.00 – 0.72)	0.92 (0.88 – 0.95)	0.93 (0.87 – 0.96)	
A_Aorta	0.59 (0.04 – 0.85)	0.89 (0.80 – 0.93)	0.89 (0.74 – 0.93)	
A_Pulmonary	0.82 (0.22 – 0.91)	0.83 (0.74 – 0.93)	0.84 (0.78 – 0.87)	
A_LAD		0.23 (0.20 – 0.77)		
A_LCX		0.23 (0.18 – 0.59)		
A_LM		0.35 (0.14 – 0.42)		
A_RCA		0.27 (0.09 – 0.61)		
V_Venacava_I	0.00 (0.00 – 0.53)	0.52 (0.39 – 0.77)	0.59 (0.46 – 0.82)	
V_Venacava_S	0.24 (0.00 – 0.36)	0.71 (0.64 – 0.83)	0.71 (0.66 – 0.83)	
Valve_Aortic		0.46 (0.33 – 0.60)		
Valve_Pulmonic		0.43 (0.21 – 0.48)		
Valve_Mitral		0.61 (0.59 – 0.66)		
Valve_Tricuspid		0.46 (0.40 – 0.55)		